

Seis –Semantic Energy Information System– provides qualified information to different agents to enable them to improve the decision-making process in their respective realms –from design to construction and refurbishment– as well as the methodologies to analyze it.

Seis offers several energy services that can be used by energy consultants, public administrations, energy certification companies, and construction companies to develop new services to enhance their business opportunities.

Seis.

A Semantic Energy Information System to integrate distributed building energy data

www.seis-system.org

If you are interested to provide data to the system or to develop and market its services, please contact us here:

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